

D6.1: Quantity of access offered

Authors:

Paola Ronzino, PIN
Achille Felicetti, PIN
Ilenia Galluccio, PIN

Ariadne is funded by the European Commission's
7th Framework Programme.

Version: 1.0 (*final*)

17th January 2017

Authors:

Paola Ronzino, PIN

Achille Felicetti, PIN

Ilenia Galluccio, PIN

Document History

- 18.12.2016 – Draft Version 0.1 Initial version of the document
- 17.01.2017 – Delivery of draft to UoY ADS for quality control review
- 20.01.2017 – Draft returned by reviewer
- 23.01.2017 – Final revision delivered by author to the project co-ordinator

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the transnational access (TNA) activities carried out in the framework of the ARIADNE project, from 2014 to 2016 as part of the activities of Work Package 6 (WP6) by PIN, Prato (Italy). It describes the programme and objectives of the training activities, and the participants' profiles and feedback.

The first activity was a week-long group visit, organized with the format of summer school on "Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC CRM", taking place in Prato between 26 and 30 May 2014. The goal of the summer school was to enable researchers and professionals to map their datasets to the CIDOC CRM standard, an exercise required to integrate them in a wider framework such as the ARIADNE one. The first activity was successful, although the number of participants was limited. Only three researchers were, indeed, able to attend the workshop, mostly due to the non availability of the other applicants to join in on the fixed dates. For this reason, the team at PIN decided to offer researchers the possibility to visit the centre as individual access, with more flexibility on the dates that were agreed in advance with the visiting researchers.

During the following years (2015-2016) PIN hosted 32 researchers as individual visits, and concluded the TNA offer with a workshop on "Legacy datasets and their inclusion in the ARIADNE Registry" hosting 13 researchers from 12-16 December 2016. In total PIN awarded 47 researchers with a scholarship. The high number of TNA fellow hosted at PIN is motivated by the interest in the topic of the course offered and also is due to the availability of PIN to accept candidates with a research project in scientific archaeological datasets. This corrective action was taken to take into account WP9 activities, which had initially stalled; the details of the corrective actions and the outcome of the course are described in the deliverable D9.1 Quantity of access offered.

The transnational access to PIN's facilities provided a summary background of the CIDOC CRM ontology, showing some case studies and some frequently used templates (e.g. for chronology, authorship, locations, etc.). PIN's TNA program attracted scholars and archaeological researchers of all levels of experience, from postgraduate students, to experienced researchers, and technician, from institutions located in 13 different European countries.

Participants proposed their case studies and research projects and learned how to transform their datasets in a CIDOC CRM compatible format for enhancing integration and for raising a wide interoperability among different archives.

The deliverable reports the results achieved, relying on the feedback given by the participants, which were collected via the TNA summary user report, at the end of each visit (reported in the appendix).

Furthermore, each participant who requested the scholarship from ARIADNE has completed the European Commission's user group questionnaire using the online form.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1 Introduction and Objectives	5
2 ARIADNE “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM”	6
2.1 Year 1 (May 24 – 30, 2014).....	6
2.2 Year 2 (2015)	9
2.3 Year 3 (2016)	10
3 Evaluation and results	14
4 Conclusions	16

1 Introduction and Objectives

This document presents the transnational access activities organised by PIN between 2014 and 2016 under WP6 of the ARIADNE project.

These activities had the aim to offer undergraduate and postgraduate students, archaeologists and data managers, the opportunity to access the ARIADNE research infrastructure, including tools and services developed within the project, by visiting the research centres that offered the TNA, either as individual or group visits.

In this context, PIN organized two user group visits, the first organized with the format of summer school on “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC CRM”, from 26-30 May 2014 and the second, as winter school on “Legacy datasets and their inclusion in the ARIADNE Registry” from 12-16 December 2016. In addition, during the course of 2015 and 2016 PIN hosted 32 individual visits.

PIN administrative assistants followed the organizational aspects, providing logistical support and information on the reimbursement process.

The applications were evaluated by the user selection panel composed by the responsible of each course, the coordinator and deputy coordinator and domain experts from outside the consortium (reported in D5.1).

Participants were invited to stay one week in Prato to learn how to map their existing datasets to CIDOC CRM, availing of the guidance and the assistance of the researchers working at PIN.

The TNA activities were organized in two modules. In the first part participants were introduced to the ARIADNE infrastructure, services and tools developed within the project. The second part was mainly driven by the projects introduced by the researchers and their proposed case studies. The main objective was to learn how to transform their datasets into a CIDOC CRM compatible format for enhancing integration and for raising a wide interoperability among different archives.

After the first year, the call for applications to the TNA provided by PIN was opened three times per year. This offered a good visibility of the course and allowed recruiting a good number of applicants.

The visibility of the course was also ensured by an intense advertisement campaign carried out by the project through all its dissemination channels, advertising it on the project web site, the newsletter, Twitter and Facebook, and during the training workshop held in the framework of archaeological conferences and symposia (CAA, EAA, EAC, and so forth).

The following sections of the deliverables are organized as follows:

- Section 2 includes the program and the quantity of attendance for each course, for 2014, and divided by years for 2015 and 2016
- Section 3 presents an evaluation of the TNA, based on the feedback of the attendees
- Section 4 reports some conclusions and considerations
- The appendix reports the TNA summary completed by each attendee at the end of their visit.

2 ARIADNE “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM”

2.1 2014 TNA (May 24 – 30, 2014)

The first edition of the ARIADNE Summer School “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM” was held from May 24th to May 30th 2014 in the premises of PIN in Prato.

The goal of the school was to enable researchers and professionals to map their datasets to the CIDOC CRM standard, an exercise required to integrate them in a wider framework such as the ARIADNE one. The school had the aim to provide a summary background of CIDOC CRM (2-3 days) demonstrating some case studies and some frequently used templates (e.g. for chronology, authorship, locations, etc.). The remaining days were dedicated to develop the mappings of students’ case studies, which they carried out under the supervision of PIN’s specialists.

The three attendees received a scholarships provided by ARIADNE to cover travel and subsistence. Their names, nationalities, affiliations, positions are reported in the following table:

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position	Period
Patrick Marko	Austrian	University of Graz	Post graduate	26-30/05/2014
Roberta Ferrito	Italian	University of Reading	Post graduate	26-30/05/2014
Emmanuelle Morlock	French	CNRS HiSoMa Laboratory, Lyon	Technician	26-30/05/2014

The detailed program of the course is reported in the next page.

**Summer School on “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM”
26-30 May 2014**

The Summer school on “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM” will be held at PIN VAST-LAB, Piazza G. Ciardi, 25, Prato (Italy) from Monday 26th to Friday 30th, 2014.

Program

<p>Monday 26 14:00-14:30</p> <p>14:30-18:00</p>	<p>Welcome and introduction to the summer school</p> <p>Introduction to the CIDOC-CRM and rationale for its use This session will give an overview on the CIDOC CRM, stressing the importance of this formal ontology as a key to overcome fragmentation of archaeological datasets.</p>
<p>Tuesday 27 09:00-13:00</p> <p>14:30-18:00</p>	<p>The CIDOC CRM: Analysis of the structure of the CRM ontology, with particular regard to classes, properties and their use for encoding information in a semantic format.</p> <p>Presentation of participants’ research Each participant will be given the opportunity to present his/her research, which will be used as test case in the sessions on Wednesday and Thursday.</p>
<p>Wednesday 28 09:00-13:00</p> <p>14:30-18:00</p>	<p>Mapping of archaeological object documentation to CIDOC CRM: Practical demonstration of how the ontology can be applied to the study and the encoding of information about archaeological objects, by mapping legacy archives in the CIDOC CRM format for data conversion.</p> <p>Mapping of archaeological site/monuments documentation to CIDOC CRM: Examples demonstrating how to implement a mapping of legacy information concerning archaeological sites and monuments to CIDOC CRM, for semantic data encoding and conversion</p>
<p>Thursday 29 09:00-13:00</p> <p>14:30-18:00</p>	<p>Mapping of archaeological object documentation to CIDOC CRM Practical exercise on mapping from participants’ documentation to CIDOC CRM.</p> <p>Mapping of archaeological site/monuments documentation to CIDOC CRM Practical exercise on mapping from participants’ documentation to CIDOC CRM.</p>

The logo consists of a stylized maze or labyrinth in yellow and green, followed by the word "ARIADNE" in large, bold, red capital letters with a white outline. A horizontal line in yellow and green runs beneath the text.

ARIADNE

Friday 30 09:00-11:00	Experiences on CIDOC CRM use International experts will share their experience with CIDOC CRM in archaeology in their work in the field and in a museum environment.
11:00-13:00	Lesson learned and feedback from participants Presentation of the results of the test cases (by the students). Evaluation of results and discussion. Closing of the summer school and final discussion.

2.2 2015 TNA

During the third year of the project, PIN offered researchers the possibility to visit its premises following individual courses on “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM” throughout the 2015.

The programme of the course was adapted to the needs of each participant, although the main structure was always the same. In particular, the first day was dedicated to the introduction of the ARIADNE infrastructure, services and tools, together with an overview of the power of CIDOC CRM ontology as a key to overcome fragmentation of archaeological datasets. During the following days each participant had the opportunity to present his/her research project and the research questions. The analysis of these elements driven the planning of the rest of the course.

Six researchers received a scholarships provided by ARIADNE to cover travel and subsistence. Their names, nationalities, affiliations, positions and participation period are reported in the following table:

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position	Period
Anja Masur	German	OEAW	Post graduate	22-26/06/2015
Cristophe Tuffery	French	INRAP	Experienced researcher	20-24/07/2015
Aybüke Öztürk	Turkish	Lumière University Lyon 2	Post graduate	21-25/09/2015
Roberta Zeni	Italian	King’s College London	Post graduate	26-30/10/2015
Daniel Löwenborg	Swedish	Uppsala University	Experienced researcher	19-22/10/2015
Amanda Karn	Swedish	Uppsala University	Undergraduate	19-22/10/2015

2.3 2016 TNA

During the last year of the project, PIN offered researchers the possibility to visit its premises following individual courses on “Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM” throughout the 2016.

The programme of the individual course was adapted to the needs of each participant, trying to keep the main structure always the same. In particular, the first day was dedicated to the introduction of the ARIADNE infrastructure, services and tools, together with an overview of the power of CIDOC CRM ontology as a key to overcome fragmentation of archaeological datasets. During the following days each participant had the opportunity to present his/her research project and the research questions. The analysis of these elements driven the planning or the rest of the course.

Twenty-four researchers received a scholarships provided by ARIADNE to cover travel and subsistence. Three researchers of the list below (marked with the * simbol), attended the course for the second time to extend the work started with the support of PIN’s experts. The names, nationalities, affiliations, positions and participation period of the attendees are reported in the following table:

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position	Period
Anaïs Guillem	French	University of Ljubljana	Post graduate	18-22/01/2016
George Bruseker	Dutch	ICS Forth	Experienced researcher	18-22/01/2016
Valentina Vassallo	Italian	The Cyprus Institute	Post graduate	18-22/01/2016
Giusy Sorrentino	Italian	The Cyprus Institute	Post graduate	18-22/01/2016
Seta Stuhec	Slovenian	OREA, Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW)	Post graduate	23-27/05/2016
Irene Maria Petschko	Austrian	OREA, Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW)	Post graduate	23-27/05/2016
Edeltraud Aspöck	Austrian	OREA, Austrian Academy of Sciences (OEAW)	Post-doc researcher	23-27/05/2016
Laura Perucchetti	Italian	Oxford University	Post-doc researcher	09-13/05/2016

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position	Period
Sarah Mallet	French	Oxford University	Post graduate	09-13/05/2016
Avgoustinos Avgousti	Cypriot	The Cyprus Institute	Post graduate	13-17/06/2016
Peter McKeague	British	Historic Environment Scotland	Experienced researcher	27/06-01/07/2016
James Chartrand	Canadian	Oxford University	Technician	18-22/07/2016
David Stott	Denmark	Moesgaard Museum	Technician	12-16/09/2016
Peter Jensen	Denmark	Aarhus University	Post graduate	12-16/09/2016
Carsten Meinertz Risager	Denmark	Unit of Archaeological IT, Moesgaard Museum/University of Aarhus	Technician	12-16/09/2016
Eleni Christaki	Greek	National and Kapodistrian Athens	Post graduate	19-23/09/2016
Laura Perucchetti*	Italian	Oxford University	Post-doc researcher	26-30/09/2016
Vanessa Cheel	British	Oxford University	Experienced researcher	26-30/09/2016
Peter Bray	British	School of Archaeology, University of Oxford	Post-doc researcher	26-30/09/2016
Ivona Posedi	Croatian	University of Lincoln, UK	Post graduate	17-21/10/2016
Ulf Jakobsson	Swedish	SND	Post graduate	24-28/10/2016
Johan Finn	Swedish	SND	Post graduate	24-28/10/2016
Anaïs Guillem*	French	FORTH	Post graduate	21-25/11/2016
George Bruseker*	Dutch	FORTH	Experienced researcher	21-25/11/2016

At the end of 2016 PIN organized a group visit in the format of winter school from 12-16 December 2016. The winter school was held at PIN, in Prato and was addressed to the ARIADNE associated partners and heritage institutions willing to share their datasets through the ARIADNE portal.

Name	Nationality	Institution	Position	Period
María José de Miguel del Barrio	Spanish	CENIEH	Post graduate	12-16/12/2016
Javier Valladolid Aguinaga	Spanish	CENIEH	Technician	12-16/12/2016
Alberto Sánchez	Spanish	Research Institute for Iberian Archaeology, University of Jaén	Experienced researcher	12-16/12/2016
Carsten Meinertz Risager	Danish	Unit of Archaeological IT, Moesgaard Aarhus	Technician	12-16/12/2016
Natalia Botica	Portuguese	Universidade do Minho	Post graduated	12-16/12/2016
Claudia Marinica	Romanian	University of Cergy-Pontoise, France	Experienced researcher	12-16/12/2016
Béatrice Markhoff	French	Université François Rabelais de Tours, France	Experienced researcher	12-16/12/2016
Maria Victoria Madrid	Spanish	Andalusian Institute of Historical Heritage	Technician	12-16/12/2016
Pilar Mondejar	Spanish	Andalusian Institute of Historical Heritage	Technician	12-16/12/2016
Peter Jensen	Danish	Aarhus University	Post graduate	12-16/12/2016
Nastasia Vanderperren	Belgian	PACKED vzw, center of expertise in digital heritage	Post graduate	12-16/12/2016
Pieterjan Deckers	Belgian	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Post-doc researcher	12-16/12/2016
Gísli Pálsson	Icelandic	The Institute of Archaeology, Iceland	Experienced researcher	12-16/12/2016
Espen Uleberg	Norwegian	Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo	Technician	12-16/12/2016

ARIADNE Winter School

LEGACY DATASETS AND THEIR INCLUSION IN THE ARIADNE REGISTRY

12-14 December 2016
PIN, room 305, 2nd floor
Prato, Piazza G. Ciardi, 25

12 December 2016

14:30 Welcome, *Paola Ronzino - PIN*
14:40 Introduction to the course, *Franco Niccolucci - PIN*
15:00 The ARIADNE Infrastructure, *Achille Felicetti - PIN*

16:00 Coffee break

16:30 Semantic Integration of Archaeological Information in ARIADNE, *Achille Felicetti*
17:00 Discussion
17:30 Workshop close

13 December 2016

09:30 Introduction second day, *Achille Felicetti*
09:40 ArSol to Semantic Web via the CIDOC-CRM, *Béatrice Markhoff - Université François Rabelais de Tours*
10:00 From ArchaeoInfo to Archaeo.dk, *Carsten Risager and Peter Jensen - University of Aarhus*
10:20 Supporting Semantic Interoperability in Conservation-Restoration Domain: the PARCOURS project, *Claudia Marinica and Cheikh Ahmed Tidiane Niang - University of Cergy-Pontoise*
10:40 Digital Field Museum and MUSIT, *Espen Uleberg - Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo*

11:00 Coffee break

11:20 Toward a long term data preservation strategy and interoperability at the French National Institute for Preventive Archaeological Research (INRAP), *Federico Nurra - INRAP*
11:40 Ísleif: the Icelandic archaeo-historical database, *Gísli Pálsson - The Institute of Archaeology, Iceland*
12:00 Deploy of CENIEH's new institutional repository, *María José De Miguel Del Barrio and Javier Valladolid Aguinaga - CENIEH*
12:20 Archaeological Heritage in the Information and Management System of Andalusia Cultural Beings, *Maria Victoria Madrid and Pilar Mondéjar - Andalusian Institute of Historical Heritage (IAPH)*

13:00 Lunch @ Soldano restaurant (directions will be given during the workshop)

14:30 MEDEA: An online platform for the reporting, recording and storage of archaeological metal-detecting finds from Flanders, *Nastasia Vanderperren - PACKED vzw, center of expertise in digital heritage and Pieterjan Deckers - Vrije Universiteit Brussel*

14:50 Bracara Augusta - Domus of Carvalheiras, *Natália Botica - Universidade do Minho*

15:10 Archaeology of the Iberians, *Alberto Sánchez - University Research Institute for Iberian Archaeology, University of Jaén*

15:30 Hands on session (Achille Felicetti, Maria Theodoridou - FORTH)

16:00 Coffee break

16:30 Hands on session

17:30 Workshop close

14 December 2016

09:00 Hands on session (Achille Felicetti, Maria Theodoridou)

11:00 Workshop close

13:00 Lunch (directions to the venue will be given during the workshop)

14:30 PARTHENOS workshop

3 Evaluation and results

All students completed both the online European Commission User Group questionnaire (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS>) and the ARIADNE TNA User Feedback Report (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Transnational-Access/User-feedback-report>).

The majority of the attendees participating at PIN's TNA were post graduate students; only one undergraduate student took part at the course:

Fig. 1: Distribution of the participants' position in their home institution

Only two participants came from a non profit/profit private organization, while twenty-four came from the University. The rest of the people enrolled came from a public research organization:

Fig. 2: Distribution of the home institutions status

The 47 TNA participants reached PIN were from institutions distributed over 13 European countries:

The overall TNA offer was positively evaluated by the attendees. In particular, in the EC Surveys all the participants expressed an overall appreciation of the course between "Good" and "Very good".

4 Conclusions

PIN provided trans-national access (TNA) from 2014 to 2016. This experience allowed us to reflect on what worked well and on what didn't.

In the first year, a week-long summer schools was organised addressing the topics of CIDOC-CRM. This attracted over nine applications from which five students were selected and three did actually attend.

Students were all expected to bring along their own projects to get support and advice and this proved to be a popular feature of the Trans-national access. The down-side of summer schools was that the fixed dates were not convenient for some applicants. This convinced PIN's team to offer the opportunity to researchers to visit the centre during the year, with more flexibility on the dates, which were decided together with the applicants.

During Year 2 (2015), the TNA was therefore expanded to include individual training placements.

This time there were ten applications, all of them were accepted. Moreover, greater interest was shown in scientific archaeological datasets, due to the possibility given by PIN to accept candidates with research project on this topic.

Attendance was higher than expected since PIN received the participation of 47 researchers out of the expected 15.

However, the real success was the individual placements for training. The research projects that the students have sought help from the experts at PIN have included mapping and conversion of excavation data recorded during excavation campaigns, CIDOC CRM description and encoding of epigraphic and textual entities, integration of scientific analysis for dating and provenance of artefacts, CRM based database design to be used in the creation of new archaeological datasets, semantic enrichment of 3D models.

The 2016 continued with the individual training on CIDOC-CRM. In addition, ARIADNE had published training materials on the portal following two very successful workshops on data management planning for archaeologists held in January. The infrastructure did also establish a good dissemination network over the last three years, especially through social media, which helped in attracting younger archaeologists to these training opportunities. However, attracting applications proved to be a challenge to start with as we had to reach the right people who, in most cases, had no prior knowledge of the institutions offering the training. Rather than launch once and then have to re-advertise to encourage more applications, in Year 2 a phased call for applications was used which worked a lot better and was more manageable.

The feedback from the TNA has also been positive – many attendees have commented that being able to get expert advice for their own research projects has been very beneficial for them.

In conclusion, the TNA on "Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM", which is part of the Work Package 6 "Legacy data and dataset design" fulfilled its objectives, by offering the attendees an overall picture of how the Semantic Web languages can be applied to the integration of legacy

datasets and to the development of new datasets in archaeology. In particular, the attendees have been given a complete view of the current state of the languages for encoding (URIs, XML) and expressing (RDF) archaeological knowledge, based on ontology in the archaeological domain (CIDOC CRM, CRMArchaeo). During its offering, the course has been modified to adjust to the background of the attendees, so that the second and third editions included a survey of the principles of semantic modelling.

Feedback were overall between good and very good.